

Supplementary Information File 5: Compression Effect Analyses

Rationale

Due to the disparity in the number of metre-related frequencies between the two metrical interpretations (two vs. four meter-related frequencies in the three- and four-beat metre interpretations, respectively), the value of \bar{z}_{EEG} and $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ are constrained to different ranges between metre conditions. In the main analysis (with registered selection of meter-related frequencies), this range goes from -1.90 to +1.90 in the three-beat metre condition, and from -1.16 to +1.16 in the four-beat metre condition. In the Supplementary Information File 4 (i.e., selection of metre-related frequencies based on the learning cues), this range goes from -1.45 to +1.45 in the three-beat metre condition and from -1.90 to +1.90 in the four-beat metre condition.

To mitigate this compression effect, \bar{z} values were normalised by linearly rescaling each condition-specific range to a common interval of -1 to +1. To account for differences in the stimulus as obtained after this normalisation (registered selection of meter-related frequencies: -0.19 for the three-beat metre condition and -0.32 for the four-beat metre condition; selection of metre-related frequencies based on the learning cues: -0.24 for the three-beat metre condition and -0.18 for the four-beat metre condition), the \bar{z} value derived from the stimulus was subtracted from the \bar{z} for each metrical interpretation.

Compression Effect for the Registered Analyses

EEG Data

The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) < 0.01$, $p = .936$, $\eta^2_p < .01$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = 1.15$, $p = .291$, $\eta^2_p = .03$. The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.42$, $p = .521$, $\eta^2_p = .01$. Overall, the results indicated that amplitude of neural responses at metre frequencies were not enhanced after vs. before the movement session (see Figure S5.1). The results are similar to the one of the main, registered analyses.

Figure S5.1

Compression-Corrected Neural Responses for the Registered Analyses

Note. Normalised, stimulus subtracted z scores at metre-related frequencies (registered selection) across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots.

Behavioural Data (Pre- and Post-Movement Sessions)

The RM ANOVA showed a significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) = 13.35, p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .26$, with larger $\bar{z}_{clapping}$ after ($M = 0.60, SD = 0.43$) when compared to before the movement ($M = 0.36, SD = 0.49, d = 0.58$). Note that the effect size is larger than the required SESOI (see Table 1 in the main manuscript), which indicated that the effect is sufficiently strong to be considered meaningful. The main effect of movement condition was also significant, $F(1, 38) = 7.51, p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .16$, with larger $\bar{z}_{clapping}$ in the four-beat metre condition (corresponding to the culturally congruent metrical interpretation; $M = 0.65, SD = 0.43$) when compared to before the three-beat metre condition ($M = 0.32, SD = 0.46, d = 0.74$). Note that here again, the effect size is larger than the required SESOI. The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.05, p = .829, \eta^2_p < .01$.

Overall, the results indicated that the amplitude of metre frequencies was selectively enhanced in the clapping responses after the movement session, with the four-beat metre condition eliciting overall higher amplitude. The results are thus similar to the one of the main analyses, with an additional main effect of condition that could be partly explained by the subtraction of a lower stimulus z score in the four-beat condition, but which is also consistent with an effect of cultural experience on rhythm processing.

Figure S5.2

Compression-Corrected Behavioural Responses for the Registered Analyses

Note. Normalised, stimulus subtracted z scores at metre-related frequencies (registered selection) across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots. *** $p < .001$

Compression Effect for the Supplementary Analyses

EEG Data

The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) = 0.73$, $p = .399$, $\eta^2_p = .02$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = 1.34$, $p = .255$, $\eta^2_p = .03$. The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.24$, $p = .629$, $\eta^2_p < .01$. Overall, the results indicated that amplitude of neural responses at metre frequencies were not enhanced after vs. before the movement session (see Figure S5.3). These findings are consistent with both the main and supplementary analyses.

Figure S5.3

Compression-corrected Neural Responses for the Supplementary Analyses

Note. Normalised, stimulus subtracted z scores at metre-related frequencies (selection based on the learning cues) across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots.

Behavioural Data (Pre- and Post-Movement Sessions)

The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session $F(1, 38) = 5.39, p = .026, \eta^2_p = .12$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = 2.06, p = .159, \eta^2_p = .05$, (see Figure S5.4). The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = .651, p = .425, \eta^2_p = .017$. Consistent with the supplementary analyses, the normalised and stimulus-subtracted behavioural responses showed a trend towards increased clapping z scores after compared to before the movement session (p slightly above the α set at .020), mirroring the direction of the significant main effect of session observed in the main analysis, but not reaching statistical significance. On the other hand, the main effect of condition in the supplementary analyses was not replicated, possibly due to the subtraction of a more negative stimulus z score favouring the non-culturally plausible three-beat condition.

Figure S5.4

Compression-Corrected Behavioural Responses for the Supplementary Analyses

Note. Normalised, stimulus subtracted z scores at metre-related frequencies (selection based on the learning cues) across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots.